

EFFECT OF LIFE SKILLS TRAINING ON SOCIAL SKILLS AND SELF-ESTEEM OF HEARING IMPAIRED STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Life skills are essentially those abilities that help promote mental well-being and competence in young people as they face the realities of life. UNICEF and WHO agree that life skills are generally applied in various aspects of life. Such as in the context of health and social events. The major objective of the present research was to investigate the effect of life skills training on social skills and self-esteem of special students in a special school setting. The study was conducted on a sample of 50 hearing impaired students aged 12-14 years studying within a special school setting. The study followed quasi-experimental design. The research was conducted through experimental method using pre-test post-test research design using a control group. The experimental and control group comprised of 25 students each and both the groups were matched on age and IQ. The pre-testing was done by Social skills scale and Self-esteem Inventory. The activity based life skills training module was prepared by the investigator herself for hearing impaired students. The experimental group of hearing impaired students was given life skills training for 30 sessions on routine basis. All the sessions were activity-based and required active participation of the students. However, the control group was given general awareness regarding health and hygiene. The treatment was followed by post-testing on social skills and self-esteem. The data were analyzed. The results of the study showed that life skills training significantly enhances social skills and self-esteem of hearing impaired students. Implications of the results are discussed.

Keywords: life skills training, social skills, self-esteem, hearing impaired students.